

CADET-Hub: Online platform for biomanufacturing modeling and stability testing

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ABSTRACT

Biomanufacturing increasingly relies on computational modeling to strengthen process understanding, speed up process development, scale-up and scale-down, improve experimental design, and reduce reliance on costly and laborious wet lab activities. Here we present CADET-Hub, a modular web-based platform for biomanufacturing and stability modeling, developed within the Inno4Vac project. CADET-Hub unifies upstream and downstream bioprocess modeling with stability prediction in a single, user accessible environment. The upstream modules comprise compartment models derived from computational fluid dynamics and metabolic models for bioreactor simulation. The downstream modules cover centrifugation, filtration, and chromatography, implemented through the open-source bioprocess simulation engine CADET-Core and its workflow and model-building layer CADET-Process. A dedicated stability forecasting module completes the platform by enabling shelf life prediction of biological products using advanced kinetic and statistical methods. Throughout the project, we engaged with regulatory bodies to inform model development, validation, and documentation in line with current regulatory expectations for biopharmaceutical applications.

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Nomenclature	
AI	Artificial intelligence
AKM	Advanced kinetic modeling
APC	Advanced process control
API	Active pharmaceutical ingredient
CADET	Chromatography Analysis and Design Toolkit
CADET-Core	High-performance C++ simulation engine of the CADET framework
CADET-Hub	Hub for computational modeling in bioprocessing
CADET-Julia	Julia simulation engine with limited functionality for rapid prototyping
CADET-Process	Workflow and model-building layer of the CADET framework
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
CI/CD	Continuous integration/Continuous deployment
CMs	Compartment models
DGSEM	Discontinuous Galerkin spectral element method
DoE	Design of experiments
DSP	Downstream processing
DTUB	Digital twin platform for upstream processing in biotechnology
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EMA QIG	EMA Quality Innovation Group
FAIR4RS	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable for Research Software
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
GUI	Graphical user interface
ICH	International council for harmonisation of technical requirements for pharmaceuticals for human use
IMI2	Innovative Medicines Initiative 2
Inno4Vac	Innovations to accelerate vaccine development and manufacture
LLFG	Listen and learn focus group
MAA	Marketing authorization application
MPC	Model predictive control
OD	Optical density
OFAT	One factor at a time
PDA	Parenteral Drug Association
PLS	Partial least squares
PoS	Probability of success
PQS	Pharmaceutical quality system
QbD	Quality by Design
RDM	Research data management
SME	small and medium enterprises
USD	Ultra scale-down
USP	Upstream processing

1. Introduction

Biomanufacturing is complex and resource intensive, requiring substantial infrastructure, specialized expertise, and often strict regulatory compliance. Capacities must adapt to fluctuating global demand, and processes must be rapidly developed for new products, yet building and

sustaining such flexibility requires substantial investment. These challenges are particularly evident in the biopharmaceutical sector, a major domain of biomanufacturing with direct impact on public health. For instance, the rapid development of mRNA vaccines during the COVID-19 pandemic showed the potential of accelerated development, while revealing limits in scaling and adaptation for new products. Emerging pathogens with high mutation rates, such as SARS-CoV-2, underscore the need for manufacturing platforms that can be reconfigured quickly to deliver safe and effective vaccines at scale.

Addressing these challenges requires systematic approaches to process design and control. Quality by Design (QbD) provides a structured framework for process design in biomanufacturing, shifting development from empirical experimentation toward systematic exploration of parameter interactions. Instead of validating quality primarily through end-product testing, QbD aims to define process conditions that consistently meet critical quality attributes by identifying robust operating ranges. Mathematical modeling and *in silico* simulation support this approach by enabling efficient analysis of parameter sensitivities, process variability, and scale-dependent effects, while facilitating regulatory compliance through improved process understanding. By capturing the underlying transport phenomena as well as biological and chemical interactions of biopharmaceutical production, these models enable prediction of process behavior under varying conditions, systematic optimization of operating parameters and stability forecasting, ensuring consistent product quality.

A variety of modeling and simulation tools for designing and optimizing biomanufacturing processes and related unit operations have been developed. These approaches differ substantially in scope and modeling perspective, depending on the application domains for which they were originally developed. Process design platforms, such as SuperPro Designer by [Intelligen, Inc. \(2026\)](#), Aspen Batch Process Developer by Aspen Technology ([Aspen Technology, Inc., 2026](#)), gPROMS by Siemens Process Systems Engineering ([Siemens AG, 2026](#)), DynoChem Biologics ([ScaleUp Company International, 2026](#)), and BioSolve Process by BioPharm Services ([Biopharm Services Ltd., 2026](#)), provide tools for designing entire flowsheets and simulating process-specific unit operations. These tools are widely used in industrial contexts for process design and scale-up. More recent integrated bioprocess modeling tools include GoSilico by [Cytiva \(2026\)](#), Ypso-Ionic by YpsoFacto ([Ypsomed Holding A.G., 2026](#)), BioContinuum by Merck ([Merck KGaA, 2026](#)), New Wave Biotech ([New Wave Biotech Ltd., 2026](#)), ChemAI ([ChemAI, 2026](#)), Basetwo AI ([Basetwo Artificial Intelligence Inc., 2026](#)), [Algocell \(2026\)](#), and Invert ([Invert, Inc., 2026](#)) with a focus on data integration, machine learning, and digital twin application for process optimization. Further, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) tools such as ANSYS CFX/Fluent ([Ansys, Inc., 2026](#)) and M-Star CFD ([M-Star Simulations, LLC, 2026](#)) provide detailed physics-based descriptions of transport phenomena at unit operation level. Finally, emerging open-source approaches, including frameworks tailored to specific applications such as mRNA manufacturing ([Shahab et al., 2025](#)), focus on modeling individual aspects of biomanufacturing within specific use cases. Despite this broad landscape, there remains an unmet need for a comprehensive, open-source, and user-friendly platform that enables the flexible interconnection of unit operations, while remaining easily extensible and applicable in both academic and industrial contexts.

In response to this need, CADET-Hub was developed within the Inno4Vac project as an integrated platform for *in silico* biomanufacturing. It covers both upstream and downstream processing (USP and DSP) and incorporates predictive models for bioproduct stability. While originally developed in the context of vaccine manufacturing and stability testing of protein subunit vaccines, the core components of the platform are molecule-agnostic and therefore broadly applicable to biomanufacturing processes. The modular design allows process steps to be combined freely, enabling flexible adaptation across a wide range of manufacturing processes ([Fig. 1](#)). While some challenges span multiple manufacturing stages, each unit operation also poses specific issues. Both general and stage specific problems can be addressed with targeted modeling approaches in CADET-Hub.

Fig. 1. Overview of the process steps and interface requirements for an *in silico* platform for biomanufacturing.

1.1. CADET-hub

CADET-Hub is a modular online platform that integrates upstream compartment and metabolic models, downstream purification models (centrifugation, filtration, chromatography, crystallization), and stability forecasting into a unified environment for biomanufacturing. Developed in close collaboration with researchers, industry leaders, and regulatory experts, CADET-Hub constitutes the *in silico* manufacturing tier of the Inno4Vac strategy. A key motivation for developing CADET-Hub was to reduce the technical overhead of setting up local software environments for bioprocess modeling.

CADET-Hub uses a server side architecture with a user friendly, browser-based interface built on JupyterHub, enabling preconfigured workflows to be run and adapted without local installation. The centrally managed software environment provides consistent version control, continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD), and seamless updates. Remote access ensures independence from local hardware, supports robust testing, validation, and long-term maintenance. For confidential use, the platform can be deployed within secured, access controlled infrastructures. Practical workflows range from data management and visualization to collaborative model development, simulation based process analysis, process design and optimization, demonstrating versatility across teams and tasks (Fig. 2).

1.2. Upstream processing

During upstream processing, scale-up is a major challenge when moving a process from the wet lab to industrial readiness. In large-scale reactors, insufficient mixing commonly leads to substrate and oxygen gradients that strongly affect productivity and yield. These gradients can be assessed by several approaches: *in situ* sensing with fixed or free-floating sensors (Bisgaard et al., 2020); reduced-order numerical modeling, such as compartment and metabolic models, to approximate concentration dynamics across conditions (Nadal-Rey et al., 2021); and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) to resolve hydrodynamics, scalar gradients, and mixing times in full spatial detail (Delafosse et al., 2014; Jaccard et al., 2014; Carfort et al., 2024). In particular, combined CFD

and metabolic models couple flow fields with process and host-cell metabolism to track quantities such as optical density, cell wet weight, protein production, and medium components. However, this level of spatial resolution comes at a cost, with simulation runtimes that can span days to weeks.

Compartment models (CMs) alleviate this computational burden by representing the reactor as a network of ideally mixed volumes connected by flows that reproduce observed mixing behavior. Historically, compartment definitions and interconnections were derived empirically or manually from CFD outputs. An automatic compartmentalization method based on CFD has since been proposed (Tajsoleiman et al., 2019), providing a simpler and standardized route to constructing CMs. In practice, regions with similar flow patterns are aggregated into larger ideally mixed zones, and metabolic models are applied in these zones, preserving essential gradient information at far lower computational cost.

Within Inno4Vac, a compartmentalization tool was developed and released as part of the standalone, cloud-enabled platform DTUB (DTUB, 2025; Li et al., 2026), enabling automatic conversion of CFD outputs into efficient compartment models that capture large-scale gradients (Spann et al., 2019).

1.3. Downstream processing

Downstream processing remains a persistent bottleneck in biomanufacturing, particularly in operations such as centrifugation, filtration, and chromatography (Shukla and Thömmes, 2010). These unit operations are essential for recovering, isolating, and purifying products such as proteins, viral vectors, or RNA from fermentation broths. While centrifugation is typically used early in the process to remove cells and particulate impurities, chromatography enables selective purification based on properties such as charge, size, or hydrophobicity, and filtration supports clarification and polishing including virus removal.

Similar to upstream processing, downstream unit operations present challenges related to scale-up and inhomogeneity. Chromatographic steps often exhibit nonlinear behavior due to complex interactions between biomolecules and the stationary phase (Carta and Jungbauer,

Fig. 2. Example of a collaborative workflow for process development enabled by CADET-Hub. Team “Experiments” generates chromatography data in the lab, which is imported, cleaned, and discussed using interactive Jupyter notebooks. Both raw and processed data are stored in a version-controlled, encrypted GitHub repository, ensuring accessibility for all team members. Team “Modeling” develops simulation software in C++, Julia, and Python directly within CADET-Hub in shareable and reproducible environments. Results are automatically versioned and linked to the codebase for full traceability. Team “Process Optimization” accesses modeling workflows and experimental data to analyze and optimize their purification processes. They provide direct feedback in the form of bug reports or feature requests via GitHub, allowing Team “Modeling” to quickly deliver updates in containerized environments and Team “Experiments” to augment the data as required. All work is conducted through a browser-based interface, eliminating local setup and enabling distributed, real-time collaboration across domains.

2010). These interactions depend on parameters such as pH, ionic strength, and mass transfer limitations. During scale-up, effects such as flow maldistribution and bed compression hinder direct translation from lab-scale to production-scale systems (Carta, 2003).

Centrifugation introduces further complexity at scale. High shear forces in industrial centrifuges can cause cell disruption, releasing intracellular components that increase the impurity load and negatively affect subsequent purification steps (Bell and Dunnill, 1982; Boychyn et al., 2001). These mechanical stresses are often not accurately captured in small-scale experiments, limiting their predictive value.

As scale-related challenges usually require extensive experimentation, modeling provides a way to streamline process design and reduce the experimental workload. Ultra scale-down (USD) methods (Boychyn et al., 2004; Rayat et al., 2016) and mechanistic simulations help bridge the gap between scales. USD systems replicate key physical features of large-scale equipment in miniaturized setups, enabling controlled and representative studies with small volumes, for example one hundredfold smaller, of feed material (Nunes et al., 2023; Voulgaris et al., 2016). Mechanistic models of chromatography and CFD based analyses of centrifugation support quantitative assessment of transport and stress phenomena, which is especially valuable in vaccine processes with high product sensitivity and purity requirements.

Beyond scale translation, models can be used to explore process variability and identify robust operating ranges. For example, mechanistic chromatography models can be combined with stochastic simulations to account for feed variability and lot-to-lot resin differences, enabling prediction of product quality across a broad range of conditions (Close et al., 2014). Such approaches reveal whether robust operating conditions exist and quantify the likelihood of meeting critical quality attributes when direct experimentation would be impractical.

A related concept within the QbD framework is windows of operation (Woodley and Titchener-Hooker, 1996), in which the feasible space for a process is mapped based on design constraints and sensitivities. These windows provide an intuitive view of safe and effective

operating zones, highlight interactions among parameters, and support decision making when multiple performance criteria must be balanced. When combined with mechanistic models, windows of operation can first identify constraints from limited data and then refine operating strategies as process understanding grows.

Because downstream steps differ in their underlying physicochemical transformations, interfacing models and software tools across unit operations can be challenging, complicating end-to-end modeling. CADET-Hub addresses this challenge by providing tools to model and connect downstream steps within a unified environment, along with methods to visualize, analyze, and optimize these processes.

1.4. Stability prediction

Stability studies are used in biopharmaceutical development to quantify degradation behavior and ensure that biological products remain within specification over time. Regulatory authorities require pharmaceutical companies to determine shelf-life for products obtained after downstream processing and final formulation, i.e. including excipients and fill-finish into final containers. Depending on the product class, additional steps such as freezing, lyophilization, or lipid nanoparticle formulation for mRNA-based vaccines are part of the manufacturing process, resulting in products that can be stored as refrigerated liquids, frozen materials, or lyophilized solids requiring reconstitution prior to administration. These different formulation states are associated with distinct degradation mechanisms and stability behaviors. Regulatory guidelines, such as the ICH Q1E guideline (ICH, 2023), serve as the primary reference for shelf-life estimation and traditionally rely on fixed-batch analysis. However, this approach is limited in its ability to represent product variability occurring in actual manufacturing processes. More robust statistical methodologies have been advocated in pharmaceutical practice for several decades. The recent draft ICH Q1 A guidance proposes incorporating hierarchical (mixed-effects) models that treat batches as random samples and improve extrapolation to future production batches (Avohou et al., 2020; Burdick et al., 2017).

As model complexity increases, for example due to unbalanced experimental designs or nonlinear stability profiles, it becomes increasingly difficult to reliably estimate confidence and prediction intervals for hierarchical models using frequentist methods (Katz et al., 1981; Burdick et al., 2017). Consequently, Bayesian methods are often required to estimate parameter uncertainty and correctly propagate errors. Additionally, Bayesian approaches enable complex probabilistic predictions that cannot be obtained using frequentist approaches (Burdick et al., 2017; Avohou et al., 2020). Since such models are fitted exclusively to data from targeted storage conditions, long-term stability predictions essentially represent extrapolations beyond the observable range. This makes predictions sensitive to model assumptions, particularly for nonlinear degradation profiles or for complex biological molecules (Clénet, 2018).

Over the past decade, methods have been developed to predict long-term stability from short-term accelerated studies using data from various storage temperatures (Clénet, 2018; Campa et al., 2021). This approach, known as advanced kinetic modeling (AKM), is especially valuable for biological products such as vaccines, which require more sophisticated methods than simple single-temperature linear regression to capture their complex degradation kinetics (Clénet, 2018; Campa et al., 2021; Neyra et al., 2021). In some cases, this approach can provide superior predictive power, even when based on as little as 100 days of data, compared to years of long-term stability measurements collected under the target storage condition. The flexibility of AKM has been demonstrated across a wide range of biopharmaceutical products, including antibodies, peptides, and vaccines in both liquid and solid dosage forms (Huelsmeyer et al., 2023; Dillon et al., 2024; Evers et al., 2022; Scaccia et al., 2025). These studies indicate that AKM can serve as a broadly applicable methodology that not only supports stability prediction but also provides utility throughout the entire product development process and product life cycle.

In this project, we developed Bayesian models for prediction of the long-term stability from recommended and accelerated storage conditions, combining AKM approaches with hierarchical modeling techniques. The models were developed and validated across a broad range of biopharmaceutical products, including monoclonal antibodies, enzymes, fusion proteins, bacteria-derived materials, diverse vaccine types, adjuvants, and peptide-based formulations. This integrated framework enables comprehensive shelf-life prediction, rigorous uncertainty quantification, and systematic assessment of the probability that product quality attributes fall outside specification limits (out-of-specification risk).

In addition, we explored how QbD, Design of Experiments (DoE), and Bayesian modeling can support vaccine formulation stability optimization (Schweitzer et al., 2010; Rozet et al., 2013; Badawy et al., 2016; Yu et al., 2014; Politis et al., 2017). While these approaches are well established in pharmaceutical development, their systematic application to vaccine stability optimization remains limited (Tome et al., 2019; Daniel et al., 2022; van de Berg et al., 2021). To address this gap, we developed an integrated modeling approach, combining QbD principles, DoE methodology, and Bayesian statistical modeling.

1.5. Process optimization and control

Model- and data-based control and optimization can support the design and operation of vaccine production processes, as well as other biopharmaceutical and pharmaceutical processes (Schmidt et al., 2022; Buckland et al., 2024; Hong et al., 2018; Jelsch et al., 2021; Eslami and Jungbauer, 2024; Vega-Zambrano et al., 2025). This requires calibrated dynamic models, where parameter estimation can become challenging, and hybrid optimization methods have been proposed to address this (Schytt et al., 2025). However, the adoption of such technologies in biopharmaceutical manufacturing lags behind other process industries, including oil and gas, chemicals, minerals, cement, steel, power, and food, where model-predictive monitoring and control have been used

for decades to improve safety, robustness, and economic efficiency (Qin and Badgwell, 2003; Bauer and Craig, 2008; Darby and Nikolaou, 2012; Christensen et al., 2025). In these industries, advanced process control (APC) and model predictive control (MPC) are now widely deployed and form the backbone of modern plant operation.

In contrast, implementation in biopharmaceutical production has been hindered by important yet stringent regulatory requirements. High profit margins have also historically reduced incentives to optimize manufacturing efficiency. However, recent studies indicate that the most successful and profitable research- and development-driven pharmaceutical companies are those that accelerated activities from drug discovery to production. This acceleration was typically achieved through digitalization and artificial intelligence initiatives carried out in consortia involving universities, small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) technology providers, and the pharmaceutical industry (Ma et al., 2022; Schumacher et al., 2023). In the Inno4Vac project, we applied and evaluated model-based control and optimization technologies tailored to biopharmaceutical production processes, including considerations relevant for regulatory documentation and approval. This work was supported by high-performance scientific computing frameworks for systems and control specifically adapted to biopharmaceutical applications.

1.6. Regulatory

Early engagement with regulatory experts is crucial as biopharmaceuticals manufacturing and process changes must comply with strict regulatory requirements designed to ensure product quality, safety, and consistency. Considering regulatory perspectives during model development ensured that the resulting framework can realistically be used within regulated vaccine development and manufacturing processes.

One of the primary benefits of process modeling is its ability to enhance the efficiency and robustness of biopharmaceutical manufacturing. Advanced modeling tools make it possible to identify potential bottlenecks, reduce variability, and minimize the risk of process failures. Importantly, modeling also facilitates the implementation of QbD principles, which aim to design processes that consistently deliver high-quality products (Ramin et al., 2024). QbD emphasizes the importance of integrating mathematical modeling tool to proactively design and control biomanufacturing processes so that they remain robust to the variation inherent in the production of biological products.

Moreover, process modeling plays a vital role in regulatory compliance. Regulatory agencies such as the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the European Medicines Agency (EMA) increasingly require detailed process understanding and well-defined control strategies as part of the approval process for new biopharmaceutical products. Modeling can substantially reduce the number of required trials by improving process understanding at both upstream and downstream stages. In downstream processing, it enhances robustness by revealing that the optimal yield of the active ingredient is often not aligned with the best conditions for impurity removal. Numerous simulations can be performed proactively and then validated through targeted physical trials, enabling the anticipation of impurity removal across multiple sequential steps and providing significant time savings during industrial process validation. Models of processes and workflows that are most directly related to product quality, such as downstream processing or, in particular, stability prediction, may have the greatest impact on both the product and the common technical document (Meln et al., 2025). By leveraging process models, companies can provide comprehensive data and insights that demonstrate their ability to maintain control over their manufacturing processes.

The modeling of biopharmaceutical processes is an indispensable tool that supports the development, optimization, and regulatory approval of biopharmaceutical products. By providing a unified and easy-to-use environment, CADET-Hub enables manufacturers to achieve higher levels of efficiency, quality, and compliance, ultimately contributing to the delivery of safe and effective vaccines and other biomolecules to patients.

2. Background

2.1. Inno4Vac

Inno4Vac (innovations to accelerate vaccine development and manufacture) is a public–private partnership of 41 leading European institutions engaged in vaccine development and production, including academic research organizations, SMEs, and large pharmaceutical companies. The project started in 2021 under the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 (IMI2), a joint program of the European Union and pharmaceutical industry associations. Inno4Vac accelerates vaccine manufacturing by developing platforms in four main areas: (1) computational systems-immunology models of vaccine effectiveness, (2) controlled human infection models, (3) cell-based 3D human infection models, and (4) *in silico* modeling of vaccine manufacturing processes and stability testing. In this paper, we focus on the results of the fourth area (Topic 4) and describe how the resulting computational tools can be accessed through a single interface and implemented at various stages of vaccine production.

2.2. CADET

The open-source bioprocess simulator CADET-Core (Leweke and von Lieres, 2018; von Lieres and Andersson, 2010), together with its workflow and model-building layer CADET-Process (Schmölder and Kasperleit, 2020) is fully integrated into CADET-Hub. These modules are part of the broader CADET framework, which has been hosted and maintained at Forschungszentrum Jülich since 2004 and serves as the codebase for a wide range of modeling tasks and computational workflows, including those developed within the Inno4Vac initiative. CADET provides a robust foundation for advanced modeling and simulation in biotechnology and supports a broad set of unit operations, including chromatography and auxiliary components such as holding tanks, valves, tubing, and detectors. These elements can be connected into complex process networks, enabling structural flexibility and closed-loop systems such as simulated moving bed chromatography. CADET has been applied in diverse use cases ranging from advanced mechanistic modeling of ion-exchange chromatography to predictive simulations of high-loading behavior and uncertainty quantification tasks (Beck et al., 2021; Borg et al., 2013; Diedrich et al., 2017; Kumar et al., 2021). The platform allows users to tailor existing models to specific process requirements or to extend modeling capabilities through custom equations, making CADET a suitable simulation backbone within CADET-Hub (Ramin et al., 2024).

CADET-Core, the original module and central component of the CADET framework, is a high-performance C++ solver for domain-specific partial differential–algebraic equations (Leweke et al., 2025). Its modular architecture enables flexible combinations of mass-transfer, reaction, and adsorption models, allowing users to assemble physico-chemical descriptions of complex processes. The solver is designed for computational efficiency and numerical robustness, providing accurate solutions of the resulting stiff and highly nonlinear systems. Shared-memory parallelization is supported through Intel threading building blocks (TBB), enabling efficient use of modern multi-core processors for fast chromatogram computation. Additionally, parameter sensitivities can be calculated using algorithmic differentiation, which supports gradient-based optimization tasks (Püttmann et al., 2016).

Considerable efforts have been made to improve the numerical efficiency of CADET-Core. The adoption of a spatial discontinuous Galerkin spectral element method (DGSEM) has substantially accelerated the solution of chromatography and related models, providing order-of-magnitude speed-ups at customary accuracy levels (Breuer et al., 2023). In addition, CADET-Julia, a new high-performance reimplementations in the Julia programming language, combines advanced numerical methods with modern, user-friendly coding practices, enabling faster prototyping and broader accessibility for biomanufacturing applications (Frandsen et al., 2025).

3. Results

3.1. CADET-hub

CADET-Hub (Lanzrath et al., 2026) is a comprehensive modeling platform within the Inno4Vac project that supports integrated biomanufacturing modeling, spanning USP, DSP, and stability forecasting. It provides both a functional environment for end-to-end simulations and a blueprint for collaborative modeling, simulation, and analysis which can be replicated to establish similar platforms in other organizational or industrial settings.

The platform is built on JupyterHub, which supports both script execution and graphical user interfaces (GUIs) within a web-accessible environment. GUI components are implemented using ipywidgets (Python) and Shiny (R), enabling flexible model configuration, execution, and visualization without requiring programming expertise. Through the GUI, users can seamlessly modify key model parameters, replace components such as unit operations, adsorption kinetics, or reaction models, and integrate their own datasets for analysis. At the same time, the underlying code remains fully accessible, allowing for advanced model customization and extension.

On the model level, this structure enables the tailoring of specific unit operations and unit operation networks to match custom laboratory scenarios. On the platform level, the modular architecture supports the addition of new GUI elements such as input forms, plots, or dashboards, and allows the integration of external Python or R packages. This design enables the straightforward incorporation of entirely new modeling frameworks or tools. The resulting flexibility ensures that both the scientific content and the platform infrastructure can be adapted as research questions or technical requirements evolve.

Centralized deployment through web browsers eliminates local setup requirements and ensures accessibility across industrial and academic partners. User management features enable fine-grained control over access to specific environments, datasets, or software components through group-based permissions. For use in industrial or confidential settings, the platform supports deployment within secured, access-controlled infrastructure, allowing data and models to remain within institutional or corporate boundaries while still benefiting from the collaborative functionality of the platform.

CADET-Hub emphasizes robust research data management (RDM) in accordance with the FAIR4RS principles, which aim to make research software findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. The JupyterHub-based environment supports efficient real-time co-development, with integrations such as GitHub and GitLab enabling transparent version control and tracking, collaborative workflows, long-term accessibility and reusability. RDM tools link datasets with their corresponding model configurations, while metadata is captured in a structured format. The use of Git Large File Storage facilitates the management of large datasets such as simulation results and experimental measurements. Together, these tools function as an electronic laboratory notebook and support the design of structured, reproducible *in silico* studies. In addition, the integration of continuous integration (CI) and continuous deploy (CD) workflows enables automated testing, validation, and deployment of notebooks and environments, further strengthening transparency, reproducibility, and long-term maintainability (see Fig. 3).

The following sections present tools, use cases, and results that demonstrate how CADET-Hub enables and accelerates modeling efforts across diverse applications, both in ongoing research and in future developments.

3.2. Regression and visualization

CADET-Hub leverages established Python packages, such as SciPy for nonlinear regression and optimization and matplotlib for plotting, to provide accessible visualization and analysis capabilities for

Fig. 3. Overview of CADET-Hub and the broader CADET environment. CADET-Hub integrates standalone modeling tools and the open-source CADET framework within a JupyterHub-based online platform. CADET provides a simulation engine, CADET-Core, and a user-friendly workflow and interface layer, CADET-Process, for detailed modeling of transport, adsorption, and reaction phenomena, as well as for digital twin applications in bioprocessing. The platform supports flexible and modular extension of model equations and promotes collaboration through reproducible workflows aligned with FAIR principles. CI/CD pipelines ensure automated testing, validation, and delivery of updates to maintain robustness and transparency across the platform.

downstream processing. The platform supports parameter estimation workflows in which mechanistic model parameters are fitted to experimental data via nonlinear least squares regression. This enables quantitative comparison of fitted parameters across operating conditions and direct visualization of model-to-data agreement.

In addition, CADET-Hub can incorporate outputs from multivariate regression approaches. Visualization routines allow users to interpret these relationships alongside mechanistic model fits, offering complementary perspectives on process behavior. The platform also supports the creation of process design visualizations, including windows of operation, to graphically represent feasible and robust operating regions based on model predictions and experimental constraints. This directly links to model-based and stochastic design space concepts, enabling robust operating conditions to be explored and communicated within the same environment.

3.3. Upstream processing

During the Inno4Vac project, an upstream compartmentalization platform was developed and published under the name Digital Twin Platform for Upstream Processing in Biotechnology (DTUB) (DTUB, 2025; Li et al., 2025). DTUB consists of three modules: (i) a module for importing CFD results, (ii) a compartmentalization tool, and (iii) metabolic modeling tools. These modules allow users to upload CFD data, derive compartmentalizations, and use these outputs for further analysis or coupling with metabolic models. For this purpose, CADET-Process was integrated to define and simulate reaction kinetics within the compartment framework, enabling the combined description of transport and reaction processes.

To improve computational efficiency, resource-intensive tasks such as compartmentalization, metabolic modeling, and postprocessing are executed on a server-side backend, while lightweight operations remain on the client side. This separation allows efficient handling of large CFD datasets and complex simulations without requiring substantial local computational resources.

DTUB provides access to multiple compartmentalization models with configurable parameters. The underlying algorithms are implemented as modular components and are accessible both via an application programming interface and independently of the platform. Further

details on the platform architecture and compartmentalization methods are provided by Li et al. (2025).

As the key functionalities and algorithms of DTUB are provided as open-source Python packages (Lund, 2025), they integrate seamlessly with CADET-Hub. Fig. 4 illustrates how the DTUB tools can be accessed via (a) the DTUB platform and (b) CADET-Hub.

3.4. Downstream processing

3.4.1. Centrifugation

Ultra scale-down (USD) centrifugation was used to compare laboratory-scale clarification performance with that of a pilot-scale disc stack centrifuge as part of the Inno4Vac project. The workflow follows the procedure described by Nunes et al. (2023) and is fully documented in the supplementary material. USD centrifugation reproduces feed zone shear and settling behavior of pilot-scale centrifuges at small scale.

Sigma theory provides the basis for matching operating conditions between scales. Clarification performance is assumed to be comparable when the ratio of volumetric flow rate to equivalent settling area remains constant ($Q/\Sigma = \text{constant}$). Non ideal flow conditions can be represented through an empirical correction factor C_f , yielding an effective settling area $\Sigma_{\text{eff}} = C_f \Sigma$. Matching Q/Σ_{eff} between pilot and laboratory scales enables the translation of USD centrifugation results to pilot-scale conditions. In the original method, the *kompAs* device is used to impose feed-zone shear; however any controlled and well-characterized shear source, including pump-based recirculation, is suitable.

The USD centrifugation workflow consists of four steps: (1) application of a defined shear exposure, (2) calculation of laboratory Sigma conditions for a selected pilot-scale operating point, (3) bench-top centrifugation under these conditions, and (4) measurement of solids remaining, supernatant optical density and endotoxin levels. Pilot-scale operating points Q1, Q2, and Q3 represent different volumetric throughputs and associated Q/Σ_{eff} values. This workflow was implemented as an interactive Jupyter Notebook within CADET-Hub. The interface allows users to enter shear settings and centrifugation parameters, performs Sigma-based calculations, and compares USD centrifugation results with pilot-scale data using built-in plotting functions.

Fig. 5 shows the graphical input interface and an example comparison of USD and pilot-scale solids remaining across Q1 to Q3.

(a) Homepage of the DTUB platform.

(b) DTUB tools in CADET-Hub.

Fig. 4. Interfaces to the DTUB tools. (a) The homepage of the DTUB platform provides a structured overview of key features. In the top-left corner, users can access platform guidelines, including instructions for navigation and use. The bottom-left corner links to user-related information, including access to GitHub resources. The main section of the homepage serves as a demonstration area, showcasing how to use the tools and functionalities of the platform. (b) Within CADET-Hub, the tools provided by the DTUB platform can be directly accessed and used inside the JupyterHub environment.

1. Run information		3. Measured results (optional)	
Run ID	0001	Sup OD ₆₀₀	
Shear	Well Spun	Solids frac	
Tube	Well Spun	ET UA/mL	
Pilot cond	Low	Pellet mL	
	Medium	Yield %	
	High	Clarity NTU	
Volume mL	2	<input type="button" value="Add run"/>	
RPM	6000		
Time min	5		
Flow L/h	100		

(a) Part of the USD workflow GUI.

(b) Pilot-scale versus USD solids remaining.

Fig. 5. Implementation of the USD centrifugation workflow. (a) GUI for entering run information, including shear conditions, tube type, Sigma-matched centrifugation settings and optional measured outputs, such as supernatant OD₆₀₀, solids fraction and endotoxin levels. (b) Example comparison of solids remaining fractions obtained from USD centrifugation experiments with pilot-scale reference values for three operating points labeled Q1, Q2 and Q3. These operating points correspond to distinct pilot-scale centrifugation conditions with different volumetric throughputs and thus different Q/Σ_{off} values.

The widget-based implementation supports scale-relevant evaluation of primary recovery operations and improves accessibility of USD workflows, supporting clearer alignment of experimental conditions between academic and industrial users.

3.4.2. Filtration and crystallization

Within the Inno4Vac project, CADET-Core and CADET-Process were extended beyond traditional chromatography modeling to also cover key downstream operations, such as filtration. A dead-end filtration module was implemented and validated, enabling prediction of filtrate fluxes, filter capacities, and fouling behavior from first principles. This advancement supports digital process development by providing mechanistic tools for filtration steps, which are particularly critical in vaccine production.

In parallel, CADET-Core and CADET-Process were extended to model crystallization and precipitation processes through population balance models based on size-discretized finite volume methods (Zhang et al., 2024, 2025; Leweke et al., 2025). A comprehensive framework including crystallization kinetics, nucleation, and growth was developed to capture particle size distributions over time. Together, the filtration and crystallization modules represent major steps toward

a unified modeling environment for biomanufacturing. Furthermore, support for multichannel and radial transport models expands the traditional axial modeling approach, enabling more detailed and realistic representations of geometries found in industrial processes.

CADET-Process complements CADET-Core by simplifying model configuration, calibration, and process optimization (Schmölder and Kaspereit, 2020). It enables users to construct and adapt models, integrate experimental data, and perform parameter estimation or sensitivity analysis. CADET-Process supports flexible configuration of modeling networks, including the arrangement and interconnection of unit operations, and provides tools to evaluate simulation results against experimental reference data or predefined key performance indicators. It also supports the implementation of optimization workflows, such as model calibration, process improvement, and design space exploration. All CADET subpackages are designed with modularity in mind, not only at the package level but also at the platform level, enabling users to interface with specific components of the framework through custom utility modules or self-developed solvers (Frandsen et al., 2025).

The following case studies illustrate how these extended capabilities can be applied within CADET-Hub, including both the calibration of

mechanistic models against experimental data and the simulation of interconnected downstream unit operations.

3.4.3. Case study I: Anion exchange capture of rP GSK

A capture step for a recombinant subunit vaccine (rP GSK) was performed on a strong anion exchange resin (Poros 50 HQ) using a 5 mL column (100 mm length, 8 mm inner diameter, column porosity 0.40, particle porosity 0.80, particle radius 7 μm). Six experiments were performed at a constant rP GSK feed concentration of 1.32 mg mL⁻¹ and load volumes of 1.98, 2.22, 2.68, 3.10, 3.56, and 4.00 column volumes (CV), corresponding to loading densities of between 2.60, 2.91, 3.52, 4.07, 4.67 and 5.25 mg mL⁻¹ packed bed. Each run followed the same protocol: pre-activation and activation, equilibration in 30 mM Tris pH 8.5, sample loading and flowthrough, rinse, a mixed buffer wash (50% Tris 30 mM pH 8.5 and 50% BisTris propane 30 mM pH 6.0, resulting pH \approx 7.1), elution with a more acidic mixture (15% Tris 30 mM pH 8.5 and 85% BisTris propane 30 mM pH 6.0, pH \approx 6.3), and stripping with 2 M NaCl. UV absorbance was monitored at 280 nm together with pH to obtain chromatograms at the column outlet. The data and metadata are shared by the experimental team.

To characterize this process, the experimental data were shared with a second team at a different location, which configured a corresponding mechanistic model using CADET-Process on CADET-Hub. A lumped rate model with pores (CADET-Core Documentation, 2025a; Felinger and Guiochon, 2004; Guiochon et al., 2006) was used for the column and combined with a multicomponent Langmuir binding model (CADET-Core Documentation, 2025b; Langmuir, 1916; Guiochon et al., 2006) with pH-dependent adsorption rate constants. Four binding components were considered: the product (A), a slightly more retained impurity (B), a late-eluting impurity whose retention time decreases with increasing loading density (C), and a strongly binding species (D) that elutes only during stripping and acts as a displacer. Because extinction coefficients of the individual species were unknown, experimental UV signals were scaled such that, for each run, the area under the 280 nm elution peak matched the total loaded mass of the modeled binding components, providing a common effective concentration scale for model comparison.

The model parameters were first calibrated manually using CADET-Process and CADET-Core by visual comparison of simulated and experimental chromatograms for all six loading densities. This was necessary because the parameter estimation problem is highly stiff: small changes in some parameters frequently led to nonconvergent simulations, thus an initial estimate is required before applying gradient-based optimization. The calibrated parameter set comprises pH-dependence factors for the adsorption rate constants of all four components, a common desorption rate, individual saturation capacities, and column transport parameters (axial dispersion and film mass transfer coefficient). Since only the total protein concentration in the feed was known, the load fractions of components B, C, and D were also treated as calibration parameters. The final feed composition used in the simulations was 1.32 mg mL⁻¹ for rP GSK (A), 0.33 mg mL⁻¹ for B, 1.01 mg mL⁻¹ for C, and 5.00 mg mL⁻¹ for the strongly binding displacer D, chosen to reproduce the relative peak areas in the elution window.

Fig. 6 compares simulated and experimental chromatograms for the six loading densities. In each panel, component A is shown in blue, B in red, C in green, and D in yellow; the total simulated concentration is shown as a solid black curve and the scaled experimental UV signal as a dotted black curve. The model reproduces the position and relative area of the rP GSK peak, its tailing due to co-elution with impurity B, and the pronounced decrease in retention time of the late impurity C with increasing loading density. Remaining discrepancies are that the simulated peaks of components A and B shift slightly to shorter times and become narrower with higher load, whereas their experimental retention times and shapes are nearly invariant, and that the load-dependent shift of component C is less pronounced in the simulations than in the data. These deviations suggest additional effects such as

restricted access of the larger, more strongly bound components C and D to a subset of binding sites or multiple site types, which are not yet captured by the current single-site Langmuir description and provide directions for future model refinement.

This case study demonstrates how CADET-Hub enables a collaborative workflow in which experimental data and mechanistic models are developed, shared, and iteratively refined across institutional boundaries. It illustrates how the platform supports the construction of a digital representation of a downstream process that captures key nonlinear and multicomponent effects relevant for biopharmaceutical applications.

3.4.4. Case study II: Filtration, storage and ion exchange chromatography

The interconnectivity of different types of unit operations, such as membrane-based separations, storage, and chromatography, is essential to model bioprocesses in full. However, the compatibility of mechanistic models across such diverse operations and the effects of their interconnection are less well explored in mechanistic modeling frameworks. A major challenge lies in aligning assumptions, timescales, and parameter definitions across models. For example, filtration is typically pressure-driven and governed by particle retention, while chromatography depends on mass transfer and adsorption kinetics.

To demonstrate how CADET-Hub addresses these challenges, a case study was conducted within Inno4Vac in which a dead-end filtration (Foley, 2006) model was coupled with an ion exchange chromatography model native to CADET. Together, these models represent a downstream process for the clarification and capture of a subunit vaccine produced in a bioreactor.

The filtration model is based on constant-flowrate cake filtration. Two sets of parameters were specified: (i) component system parameters, including concentrations of feed components, densities, molecular weights, solvent viscosities, and specific cake resistances; and (ii) filter parameters, including membrane area, clean filter resistance, applied flowrate, and a rejection model. At present, the available cutoff rejection model is based on molecular weight. Here, components with a molecular weight larger than a defined threshold are fully retained, while smaller components permeate. Retained components accumulate as a filter cake, contributing to the pressure drop across the filter. Simulations were performed with the CADET-Python-Simulator (Schmölder and Klaus, 2025), and the complete example case study can be accessed on GitHub (Daniel Espinoza, 2025).

The chosen chromatography model was the general rate model (CADET-Core Documentation, 2026a; Gu, 1995; Kučera, 1965; Felinger and Guiochon, 2004; Guiochon et al., 2006) with strong anion exchange binding (CADET-Core Documentation, 2026b; Møllerup, 2008; Huuk et al., 2017) that captures three components: two impurities and one product. To mimic realistic displacement during elution, a hypothetical fourth component (displacer) was introduced. The displacer was assumed to originate from the permeate stream of the filter and was included in the chromatography model as part of the component composition. This enabled the simulated elution to reproduce the competitive displacement of bound species without requiring a separate model type. Fig. 7 shows the process layout: a Sartobran[®] P 0.2 μm filter (0.1 m² area) (Sartorius, 2025) removes cell debris before the clarified harvest is loaded onto the ion exchange column. Intermediate storage vessels between the units enable batch-wise operation and act as decoupling points for data exchange.

The filter resistance was computed from the product data sheet using the pressure-flowrate chart and Darcy's law, $R_f = \Delta p / (\mu J)$, where R_f is the filter resistance, μ the dynamic viscosity of the permeating liquid, Δp the pressure drop across the filter, and J the filtrate flux defined as the volumetric flowrate per unit area. A total volume of 28 L was set to be filtered at a flowrate of 10 L/h.

The bioreactor harvest was modeled as a mixture of lysed cell particles and proteins. The proteins were lumped into a single component with an assumed molecular weight of 82.4 kDa. Cell debris

Fig. 6. Simulated and experimental chromatograms for the rP GSK capture case study at six loading densities. Component A is shown in blue, B in red, C in green, and D in yellow. The total simulated concentration is shown as a solid black curve and the scaled experimental UV signal as a dotted black curve. Panels (A) to (F) correspond to different runs with increasing column volume (CV) and loading densities in mg/mL. The rP GSK concentration was 1.32 mg/mL for every run.

was represented by two additional components with molecular weights 1000 and 1500 times larger than the proteins. The densities of proteins and debris were set to 10% higher than that of water at 25 °C, and the solvent viscosity was set to that of water at the same temperature. Cake resistances were qualitatively approximated at a value of 10^{15} for debris components and 0 for proteins and water.

The filtration model predicted complete retention of cell debris, as expected from the step cutoff rejection model. The simulation tracked the buildup of cake resistance and the resulting pressure drop, which increased linearly from an initial 1.5 kPa to approximately 4.7 kPa after filtering 28 L of feed, well below the filter's rated limit of 50 kPa. Concentration profiles of permeating and retained species were monitored throughout the operation. The resulting chromatogram at the column outlet is shown in Fig. 8, where the product is the blue line, impurities are green and red and the displacer component is shown in yellow. The pH is the black dashed line on the second axis. Both figures show the same chromatogram on different scales.

This integrated simulation confirmed that mechanistic models for distinct unit operations can be made compatible within the CADET

framework, provided that interfaces are carefully designed. In this case, explicit storage vessel models allowed local material balances to be closed and component concentrations to be transferred in a structured and physically interpretable way. Batch mode operation simplified time alignment between models, while consistent mapping of component identities and units ensured a coherent interpretation of species properties and concentrations.

The case study also illustrates how upstream variability, such as changes in biomass composition or cell disruption efficiency, can be propagated downstream to predict its impact on subsequent unit operations. In this case study, the filter resistance from the product sheet was used only to enable a functional demonstration of the coupled workflow. This value represents clean water resistance and does not reflect the higher and often time-dependent resistance seen with real feeds. In our setup, the assumed resistance shapes the predicted pressure profile but affects the chromatography step only by determining the permeate composition passed to the storage vessel. For realistic use, resistance data and fouling behavior must be measured experimentally for the specific feed, and these would replace the illustrative value applied

Fig. 7. Flowsheet of the simulated downstream process, showing filtration, intermediate storage, and anion exchange chromatography.

Fig. 8. Chromatography simulation: Elution profiles at different scales. The product is shown in blue, impurities are green and red and the displacer component is shown in yellow. The pH is the black dashed line on the second axis.

here. Although experimental validation of the filtration model is still required, particularly for sieving behavior and cake resistance values, the simulation provides a foundation for flowsheet-level mechanistic modeling. The openly available simulation code can be extended to include upstream operations such as homogenization and bioreactors, advancing CADET-Hub toward a fully integrated, end-to-end bioprocess modeling tool for biomanufacturing.

3.5. Process optimization and control

Biopharmaceutical production processes, including those studied in the Inno4Vac project, are inherently batch-based. The upstream reactor is operated in fed-batch mode, and the downstream unit operations (centrifugation, filtration, chromatography) are executed as discrete batch steps. As illustrated in Fig. 9, process development in laboratory environments increasingly relies on advanced process control systems to coordinate operations and accelerate development cycles. The batch nature of the vaccine production requires a combination of sequence control, which orchestrates the order and timing of unit operations, and nonlinear model predictive control, which optimizes individual steps such as fermentation, centrifugation, filtration, and chromatography (Tallvod et al., 2022; Espinoza et al., 2024).

Within the Inno4Vac project, simulation studies demonstrated the feasibility and economic impact of model-based technologies and digital twins for the design, operation, and optimization of biopharmaceutical processes. Systematic data collection in a data lake is essential for enabling the monitoring, control, and optimization algorithms constitute advanced process control systems. Digital twins can reduce experimental effort and support process optimization. Since biopharmaceutical production processes are complex and often operated conservatively, simulations showed that upstream yield can be increased by more than 50% using model-based optimization. Similarly, in a downstream chromatography use-case, model-based optimization and control increased productivity from 1.75%/min in the base case to 2.10%/min in the optimized case at equal purity, corresponding to a 20% improvement. New sensors and feedback-enabled control offer opportunities to operate biopharmaceutical processes in ways that make product quality more robust and less sensitive to process variations while simultaneously increasing yield. More details will be published in a separate paper. In this context, the CADET-Hub platform serves as a blueprint for establishing a dedicated modeling and simulation platform on company servers that preserves data confidentiality for industrial applications.

Fig. 9. Biopharmaceutical laboratory environment equipped with an advanced process control system.

Fig. 10. Comparison of long-term data hierarchical Bayesian modeling versus AKM approaches for shelf life determination. The left panel shows the raw data at the three storage conditions (5, 25 and 40 °C). The right upper panel shows the results of a non-linear Hierarchical model fitted on the target storage condition only. On the right lower panel, the graph shows the AKM approach incorporating multiple temperatures. Lines and points represent the stability profiles over time, with dotted red lines indicating the specification limit. Dark and light-colored shaded areas represent 95% prediction (PI) and confidence intervals (CI), respectively. Far right panels show specification compliance probability over time for future batch means. The comparison demonstrates the enhanced predictive capability of the AKM through multi-temperature data integration.

3.6. Stability prediction

Within the Inno4Vac project, a statistical framework for stability assessment that integrates hierarchical models, Bayesian inference, and Advanced Kinetic Modeling (AKM) was developed. The framework enables shelf-life prediction of biological products using either long-term stability data collected at the intended storage condition (5 °C for many vaccines), or using data generated under various storage conditions (accelerated storage conditions; e.g. 25, 35 and 40 °C).

For stability assessment based on long-term data at the intended storage condition only, mixed-effects models were used to treat batches as random samples from the production process, allowing generalization to future batches. Both frequentist and Bayesian implementations were evaluated, with Bayesian methods offering greater flexibility and more informative uncertainty quantification, particularly for non-linear profiles or unbalanced designs (Avohou et al., 2020; Burdick et al., 2017). Posterior predictive distributions support the computation of confidence and prediction intervals, as well as the probability of specification compliance, a regulatory-relevant risk metric referred to as probability of success (PoS) (Burdick et al., 2017; Hahn and Meeker, 1991).

To enhance predictive capability by incorporating data from accelerated storage conditions, we implemented hierarchical AKMs based on thermokinetic reaction functions (e.g., truncated Šesták–Berggren model (Roduit et al., 2014; Šesták and Berggren, 1971)). These models incorporate temperature-dependent degradation mechanisms, enabling long-term stability extrapolation to the intended storage condition from elevated-temperature data (Roduit et al., 2014; Clénet, 2018; Campa et al., 2021). AKMs can be applied to stability predictions across multiple modalities (e.g. conventional and mRNA-based products, peptides, and biotherapeutics) highlighting their suitability for shelf-life assignment across a broad range of products and storage forms (e.g. frozen, liquid, solid). Multiple sources of variability typical of stability studies (e.g. batch-to-batch or run-to-run variability) were integrated using hierarchical Bayesian modeling. The developed AKM framework supports both simple linear profiles (zero-order kinetic) up to more complex multi-step mechanisms and, through its hierarchical structure, enables predictions applicable to future batches. Bayesian inference allows a straightforward estimation of kinetic parameters and derived quantities, addressing known limitations of bootstrap-based uncertainty estimation (Chau et al., 2023; Huelsmeyer et al., 2023). Case studies based on real vaccine data demonstrated that posterior-based PoS is a useful tool for supporting shelf-life assignment. Fig. 10

Table 1

Recent regulatory guidance documents relevant to process modeling and AI in pharmaceutical development.

Regulatory Body /Organization	Guidance (Year, Title, Section)
ICH	2011 Q8-10 Points to Consider (PTC) document (Section 5: Role of models in QbD) (ICH, 2011)
ASME	2023 Q13 Continuous Manufacturing (Section 3.17: Process Models) (ICH, 2023) 2018 VVUQ 40 – VVUQ in Computational Modeling of Medical Devices (ASME, 2018) (in preparation) VVUQ 80 – VVUQ in Computational Modeling of Pharmaceutical Products (ASME, 2025)
EMA	2024 Reflection paper on the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the medicinal product lifecycle (EMA, 2024b) 2024 EMA QIG Preliminary Considerations on Process Models (EMA, 2024a)
FDA	2023 Assessing the Credibility of Computational Modeling and Simulation in Medical Device Submissions (FDA, 2023b) 2023 Artificial Intelligence in Drug Manufacturing and Using Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in the Development of Drug and Biological Products (FDA, 2023a) 2025 Considerations for the Use of Artificial Intelligence to Support Regulatory Decision-Making for Drug and Biological Products (FDA, 2025)

illustrates the enhanced predictive capability of AKMs through multi-temperature data integration compared to a model based only on the target storage condition.

The models were developed and validated using approximately 30 blinded datasets provided by industrial collaborators covering a wide range of bio-pharmaceutical products, including liquid and lyophilized monoclonal antibodies, enzymes, fusion proteins, bacteria-derived materials, split-virus, multivalent polysaccharide vaccines, lyophilized vaccines, protein-based and live viral vaccines, oil-in-water emulsion adjuvants, and peptide-based formulations. Our results demonstrate that integrating hierarchical modeling and AKM within a Bayesian framework enables robust estimation of vaccine shelf life while meeting expectations of regulatory authorities for statistical justification. The proposed approach aligns with the principles of ICH Q12 on life cycle management and growing regulatory openness to model-informed stability assessment (Campa, 2022; Neyra et al., 2021).

Another part of the project focused on enhancing vaccine formulation stability by integrating QbD principles with DoE and Bayesian methods. Despite recent work in this field (Daniel et al., 2022; van de Berg et al., 2021), the systematic application of QbD principles to vaccine stability optimization remains limited. In traditional vaccine stability assessment, formulation parameters are often varied one factor at a time while others are kept constant. Such one-factor-at-a-time (OFAT) approaches are not well suited for capturing interactions between formulation factors and typically require substantial experimental effort to achieve reliable estimates of factor effects (Parr and Schmidt, 2018; Basso et al., 2018; Peraman et al., 2015; Peterson, 2008). In contrast, DoE enables the simultaneous evaluation of multiple factors and their interactions, supporting the identification of relationships between formulation parameters and critical quality attributes (Tome et al., 2019; Politis et al., 2017).

For this, a QbD approach for stability optimization of a recombinant protein-based vaccine and a live-attenuated virus (freeze-dried) vaccine were implemented in collaboration with an industrial partner. In the initial screening phase, we used DoE methodology to evaluate several excipients (up to seven) and assessed their impact on vaccine quality at release and after accelerated storage conditions (25, 37 and 40 °C). Through Bayesian analysis of the experimental data, we identified the design space by examining parameter combinations that yielded higher probabilities of meeting vaccine specifications both at release and after two weeks at 37 °C (Peterson, 2008; Basso et al., 2018; Parr and Schmidt, 2018; Politis et al., 2017; Rozet et al., 2013). This ongoing work examines how these key parameters influence vaccine quality under both release conditions and in accelerated stability studies, while the design space is defined using Bayesian methods by identifying

parameter combinations with high PoS compliance at both release and shelf life.

This integrated approach represents an advancement over traditional vaccine development methodologies, offering a more systematic and scientifically grounded framework for stability optimization. By combining QbD principles with advanced statistical modeling and accelerated testing strategies, the methodology enables more efficient exploration of formulation stability while supporting robust product performance. The corresponding workflows for the stability prediction were implemented as open-source R and STAN scripts and integrate into CADET-Hub via a Shiny interface.

3.7. Regulatory

For the models developed within Inno4Vac to be fully implemented in vaccine development, manufacturing, and testing, it is critical that their outputs align with regulatory expectations (Table 1), as the final products developed using such models will require registration and need to receive market authorization in order to become available for patients. Proactive planning and early dialogues with regulators were therefore considered essential to the success of the project. These activities focused on (1) guiding developers through the relevant regulatory landscape to ensure consideration of these during development and validation, and (2) promoting early exchange on the recent methodological developments between consortium members and regulators involved in assessing vaccine registration files. Through these interactions, the platform developers shared their initial model construction work with regulators and received valuable feedback to inform further development and regulatory usability of the platform.

The dialogue included two regulatory workshops between the Inno4Vac consortium and representatives of various European regulatory agencies and Health Canada, involving an open exchange of information and questions (Meln et al., 2025). The consortium also discussed the incorporation of computational models into the regulatory process with the Quality Innovation Group (QIG), a working group hosted by the EMA. These conversations reinforced that regulators are open to the use of models in future vaccine registration files, provided that appropriate method validation is performed. As an example, during a 2023 QIG 'Listen and Learn Focus Group (LLFG) meeting', members of Inno4Vac presented their progress on CFD-derived compartment models combined with metabolic models for fast development, scale-up and control of vaccine manufacture (upstream processing). It was discussed that explicit filing and subsequent maintenance of algorithms/equations might not be required in the dossier, and that changes to the models could be covered by Companies' Pharmaceutical Quality System (PQS) (European Medicines Agency, 2023). Such dialogues

Fig. 11. The overall use of the online model platform for model assisted vaccine development in the Inno4Vac project.

must be continued as the computational models become increasingly incorporated in vaccine production and testing (see Fig. 11).

4. Summary and conclusions

This paper presents the novel *in silico* framework CADET-Hub for biomanufacturing addressing both upstream and downstream processes within a unified modeling environment. The framework integrates elements relevant to system control, supports process stability assessments, and aligns with emerging regulatory guidance for model-informed development. The following paragraphs summarize each of these key components.

The upstream bioprocessing modeling using CFD and metabolic models can substantially enhance our understanding of bioreactor dynamics and cellular expression systems. As these models become increasingly validated, they are expected to support predictions of scale-up effects, optimization of media and feeding strategies, and improvement of reactor configurations. Future work will involve integrating the presented models into real-world production projects and expanding available datasets to further refine the underlying metabolic models and improve predictive accuracy. Broadening the application of bioprocess modeling has potential to streamline process development, reduce experimental workload, and inform real-time process control, thereby contributing to more efficient development of biopharmaceutical products.

Downstream processing continues to evolve through the integration of mechanistic understanding and advanced model-based approaches. Purification steps such as centrifugation, filtration, and chromatography, long established in bioprocessing, are increasingly enhanced by predictive models that can be applied within a unified modeling platform. CADET-Hub enables process analysis and design utilizing experimental data as well as process optimization with respect to key performance indicators (Section 3.4.2). Visualization tools for scale-down models, when combined with process modeling, support improved interpretation of scale-up behavior and can reduce experimental effort during process validation (Section 3.2). At the industrial level, these capabilities facilitate more robust and efficient manufacturing, with chromatography modeling allowing systematic exploration of the design space. Using *in silico* experiments and mechanistic modeling, Inno4Vac has streamlined unit operations in biomanufacturing, particularly within DSP, including chromatography and filtration. While the methodology is currently being applied by Sanofi Pasteur for a vaccine candidate in Phase II, the goal is to extend the presented *in*

silico modeling approaches to all manufacturing stages, including USP, thermostability assessments, and fill-finish operations. Looking ahead, the continued development and application of integrated modeling frameworks and digital twins have the potential to accelerate process development, reduce experimental burden, and inform real-time decision-making (Section 3.4.4). Collectively, these advancements support a shift toward more agile, data-driven biomanufacturing strategies for biopharmaceutical products.

Stability prediction can be advanced by evaluating how AKM combined with Bayesian statistics enhances and accelerates pharmaceutical stability assessment. By leveraging accelerated stability data through differential kinetic models, these approaches enable extrapolation of long-term stability from short-term studies. The Bayesian framework provides a risk-based approach to shelf-life determination with comprehensive uncertainty quantification and appropriate propagation of experimental and model uncertainties. Case studies using industrial partner data indicate that AKM can offer improved predictive capability compared to conventional single-temperature approaches, particularly for complex biological products such as vaccines. These models have been implemented in R and STAN and will be made available at the end of the project with a Shiny interface to facilitate broad adoption across the pharmaceutical industry.

Complementary to these advances, QbD and DoE principles have been implemented to identify critical formulation factors affecting vaccine stability. By combining Bayesian inference with QbD-driven experimental design, key determinants of formulation stability could be systematically evaluated, and a Bayesian design space for vaccine stability has been generated. This approach not only improves scientific understanding of stability determinants but also supports robust formulation development through model-based simulation.

While current regulatory frameworks primarily rely on conventional single-temperature stability models, European regulators have expressed openness to statistically justified alternatives. Our work indicates that more flexible regulatory data packages could, in the future, support model-based predictions informed by short-term accelerated data, an approach currently not permitted, and thereby potentially facilitate earlier regulatory submissions under defined conditions. Successful implementation will require addressing several key challenges through continued research and dialogue with regulators. These include robust sensitivity analyses, validation through retrospective comparisons, assessment of model performance under sparse data scenarios, and evaluation of generalizability across products.

Ultimately, this work provides a foundation for more efficient and scientifically rigorous approaches to stability assessment that have the

potential to accelerate aspects of pharmaceutical development while maintaining regulatory robustness. Broader adoption of these methods could mark an important step toward predictive, model-informed stability assessment with reduced development timelines, offering particular value during public health emergencies such as pandemics.

5. Outlook

CADET-Hub is a comprehensive and open-access modeling platform designed to accelerate innovation in biomanufacturing, with vaccine production as a key use case. By combining USP and DSP modeling, system control, and regulatory insights, it provides a shared digital environment that bridges academic research and industrial application. Through integrated tools for version control and data exchange, CADET-Hub supports transparent, reproducible, and interdisciplinary collaboration, acting as a catalyst for the development of novel bioprocesses within the Inno4Vac project and beyond.

From an industry perspective, open source modeling tools have long offered superior flexibility and customization compared to other bioprocess simulation tools, but they have been less accessible for users without programming expertise. CADET-Hub closes this gap, making it not only a viable competitor to other modeling tools but also offering unique advantages in terms of integration, flexibility, and collaborative functionality.

The platform is in active development and supports real-time interaction through both code and graphical interfaces. Its modular architecture enables seamless integration of diverse modeling tools and programming languages, allowing contributors from different domains to work within a unified framework. This flexibility enhances scientific rigor while facilitating efficient translation of research outputs into industrial practice.

Future extensions will strengthen scalability, security, and reproducibility. Container orchestration will allow dynamic allocation of computational resources, ensuring that simulations from routine analyses to computationally intensive optimization tasks are executed in consistent and reproducible environments. In parallel, an access control system will provide secure authentication and fine-grained user management, coupled with encrypted, version-controlled data storage. This setup balances academic openness with industrial confidentiality, ensuring controlled yet flexible collaboration.

In the long term, CADET-Hub is envisioned as a transferable blueprint for future modeling initiatives. Its modular and extensible design supports reuse across domains, promoting sustainability and interoperability of workflows. By aligning with FAIR4RS principles and best practices in software engineering, scientific computing, and data stewardship, the platform lays the foundation for resilient, collaborative, and innovation-driven digital bioprocess development.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Eric Calvosa and Didier Clenet are employed by Sanofi and Noémie Mansois by CapGemini. Antonio G. Cardillo and Mónica Perea-Vélez are employees of the GSK group of companies. Authors may hold shares and/or stock options in their respective companies.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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